

1 **Guidance for the assessment of health interventions in the wildlife trade**

2

3 Craig Stephen^{1*}, Chris Walzer^{2,3}, Colmán Ó Críodáin⁴, Prishani Vengetas⁵, Clements
4 Meseko⁶, Sascha Knauf^{7,8*}

5

6 ¹McEachran Institute, Nanoose Bay, BC, Canada, craigstephen.pes@gmail.com

7 ²Wildlife Conservation Society, New York, NY, United States of America,

8 ³Research Institute of Wildlife Ecology, University of Veterinary Medicine, Vienna, Austria

9 ⁴Policy and Biodiversity Practice, World Wildlife Fund International, JB Zeist, The
10 Netherlands

11 ⁵Policy and Biodiversity Practice, World Wildlife Fund International, JB Zeist, The
12 Netherlands

13 ⁶National Veterinary Research Institute, Vom, Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria

14 ⁷Institute of International Animal Health/One Health, Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut, Federal
15 Research Institute for Animal Health, Greifswald - Insel Riems, Germany,
16 sascha.knauf@fli.de

17 ⁸Professorship for One Health/International Animal Health, Faculty of Veterinary
18 Medicine, Justus Liebig University, Giessen, Germany

19

20 *Corresponding authors

21

22

23

24 **Preamble**

25 Although wildlife is not a driving factor for epidemics, wild animals – especially when
26 traded – play an important role as a source for (re-)emerging pathogens that can impact
27 the health of farmed and domestic animals as well as humans (Karesh et al., 2005, 2012;
28 Hilderink and Winter, 2021). Some examples are the outbreaks of SARS-CoV (Wang and
29 Eaton, 2007), psittacosis (Abdullah et al., 2024) or mpox (Diseases, 2003). While there
30 are equally considerable health risks for wildlife from the contact with domestic and farm
31 animals and or humans, as for example seen in SARS-CoV-2 infected deer (McBride et
32 al., 2023), this guiding document focuses on the assessment of health interventions for
33 humans in the trade of wildlife. We applied the definition of wildlife trade published
34 elsewhere: “The commerce in wildlife species, inclusive of parts and products derived
35 from them. This is inclusive of both local/domestic and international commerce and both
36 legal and illegal taking, use, and trade.”¹ We consider this definition to apply to terrestrial
37 and aquatic species. Wildlife trade has significant economic value both in legal and illegal
38 trade (Sas-Rolfes et al., 2019). Its regulation is a global multi-stakeholder challenge with
39 feedback and interactions between individual actions and socio-cultural, socio-economic
40 and ecological structures and norms that span several scales and changes over time.

41 Studies and experiences suggest that a reduction in the trade of wildlife can be
42 beneficial to human and environmental health. It is, however, unlikely that the trade of
43 wild animals, in its many legal and illegal forms, will be eliminated in the foreseeable
44 future. Therefore, decision-makers need to understand the effectiveness of their
45 interventions. Researchers and decision makers are not only facing the task of

¹ <https://alliance-health-wildlife.org/https-alliance-health-wildlife-org-wp-content-uploads-2025-02-updated-glossary-int-alliance-against-health-risks-in-wildlife-trade-pdf/>

46 accumulating evidence on the presence (or absence) of pathogens, their locations in the
47 supply chain and their spillover to new hosts, or on risky human behaviours but also –
48 most importantly – to identify effective ways to prevent and mitigate health risks within
49 complex economic and ecological landscapes that in many cases span multiple countries.

50 Evaluation is a systematic and flexible approach to learning about and improving
51 the value of intervention programs and policies. In wildlife trade, it can increase the quality
52 and safety of interventions and increase accountability to stakeholders, funders, and the
53 public. Program evaluations inform decisions and identify options for program
54 improvement. The current lack of systematic program evaluations or implementation
55 studies in combination with often conservative administrative structures makes it difficult
56 for decision makers to select interventions most likely to be efficient, acceptable, effective,
57 and sustainable within and across the socio-economic and ecological context of wildlife
58 trade (Stephen et al., 2022). Considering the diversity of species and their products,
59 people, and places involved in the wildlife trade, a one-size-fits-all approach to evaluation
60 is not feasible.

61

62 **Objective**

63 The objective of this guiding document is to create a framework for implementation
64 science and evaluation of health risk reduction efforts in wildlife trade that provides advice
65 and guidance on the types of questions, considerations and approaches that should be
66 considered when one is trying to customize an evaluation for a specific intervention. We
67 are proposing a conceptual framework to promote the uptake and adaptation of
68 implementation science and program evaluation thinking in wildlife trade. We aim to

69 strengthen evidence-based practices to reduce the risk of pathogen transmission within
70 the wildlife trade.

71 The magnitude, frequency and scope of health risks associated with the trade of
72 wild animals is context specific and varies over time. Yet, the health consequences are
73 substantial and warrant global calls for risk prevention and mitigation interventions
74 ((OHHLEP) et al., 2023). People are now recognising the importance of asking questions
75 like, “What strategies are best suited to the local social conditions of their
76 implementation?” and “What level of interventions yields effective, acceptable, and
77 sustainable change?” to design effective and sustainable interventions to reduce health
78 risks in wildlife trade. This is the realm of implementation science and program evaluation,
79 which is unfortunately not widely applied in the complex environment of wildlife trade
80 (Stephen et al., 2022). An evidence-based approach to risk management needs to move
81 beyond discovering what works and why, to what works for whom and under what
82 circumstances. Actions to manage risks in wildlife trade need to shift from advocating for
83 one reductionist approach towards integrated systems thinking that incorporates the
84 socio-economic context (Thomas-Walters et al., 2020).

85 We note that our proposed framework has never been applied or evaluated in
86 terms of reliability or adaptability, nor has it been validated. It is designed to highlight core
87 needs and to propose feasible solutions for program evaluation in complex health issues
88 in wildlife trade. It is intended to foster implementation science that supports system- and
89 evidence-based risk reduction interventions in the management of wildlife health and the
90 trade of wild animals.

91

92 **State of evaluation science in complex systems such as the wildlife trade**

93 Some of the first frameworks to accelerate the mobilization of health knowledge into
94 action implicitly characterized the movement from discovery research into
95 epidemiological trials, then to real-world applications as a seemingly linear process
96 (Braithwaite et al., 2018). In practice, the process is much more complex. Insufficient
97 understanding of relationships between the context of an intervention and the process of
98 its implementation has been cited as a critical cause of the ongoing gap between research
99 and practice (Pfadenhauer et al., 2017). Implementation models are beginning to consider
100 the context and process of implementing an intervention. Concepts from complexity
101 science are integrated to consider the dynamic properties of socio-cultural-ecological
102 systems that generate health risks or affect health practice uptake. This considers
103 multiple forces, variables, and influences impacting the change process and the inherent
104 unpredictability of complex adaptive systems (Braithwaite et al., 2018).

105 Evidence-based strategies are essential to ensure that interventions maximize
106 their beneficial impacts, especially when resources are limited and there is urgency to
107 act. There is, however, a paucity of published literature on systematic evaluations of
108 health interventions in the wildlife trade (Cheng et al., 2017; UNep, 2019; Stephen et al.,
109 2022). This is partly due to the practical challenges of gathering evidence in the trade and
110 the lack of investment in evaluation and implementation studies (Stephen et al., 2022).
111 However, even when evidence exists, there can be barriers to its acceptance or
112 implementation (Arias et al., 2021).

113 The translation of emerging infectious disease research into policy into action is
114 context-laden, time-consuming, and not linear. Administrative and budgetary

115 responsibilities are traditionally divided between the human, animal and environmental
116 health sectors. As a result, the traditional lack of a system-based approach (One Health),
117 plus a shortfall of structured program evaluations, limits the capacity to predict the
118 likelihood of program implementation success (Nilsen, 2020).

Evidence that an intervention could change an outcome is not the same as evidence
to show that the process for implementing the intervention is feasible, acceptable,
efficient, effective, ethical, affordable, and or sustainable.

119

120

121 **One size does not fit all**

122 Generally, there are three steps in the knowledge-to-action process: (i) identify and clarify
123 the problem, (ii) build and test solutions tailored to the context of their application, and (iii)
124 implement, evaluate, and sustain the solutions (Lockwood et al., 2016). Unfortunately,
125 none of these linear steps are straightforward in wildlife trade. The trade for example
126 includes legal and illegal components that co-occur, and which are by nature variably to
127 non-controlled. Regulation "is challenging due to its breadth, scale and the myriad species
128 and products involved" (IPBES, 2020). Health issues in the trade of wild animals are
129 generally context-specific, involve multiple stakeholders, some with conflicting values,
130 interests, rights and needs. Due to the complex interactions in wildlife trade, there is no
131 assurance that a risk reduction program can predictably and regularly lead to changes in
132 the risks of interest, especially when compared to the counterfactual scenario in which no
133 (or a different) intervention occurred. Success requires alignment of an intervention with
134 needs; resources and capabilities; priorities and culture; mechanisms for sustainability;
135 and the regulatory environment.

136 Since human behaviour, policies and practices are the ultimate driving force for
137 pathogen spillover, the origins, and control of potential health risks, including the
138 impediments and enablers of risk reduction, are often challenged by the deeply rooted
139 socio-cultural-ecological context in which wild animals or their products are traded. As a
140 result, interventions must be delivered and evaluated at different levels, from individual to
141 societal to ecosystem scale, as well as from the local to global level.

142 Many factors affect whether an encounter with the wildlife trade will result in an
143 adverse human health impact. It is conceptually and operationally hard to account for all
144 the complicated and interdependent relationships between different elements of wildlife
145 trade to track the pathways through which different actors and actions can result in
146 predictable and sustainable risk reductions.

147

148 **Implementation science as the entry point for program improvement and** 149 **evaluation**

150 An evidence-based risk reduction program generally needs to answer two core questions:
151 (1) What evidence exists to determine who needs to do what to make the necessary
152 changes that lead to the targeted risk reduction? and (2) What are the individual,
153 organizational, or systems features and processes that need to be in place to allow the
154 necessary changes? Concerns have been raised that lack of attention to the first question
155 risks unethical, ineffective, or counterproductive outcomes for wildlife, ecosystems, and
156 people (Sas-Rolfes et al., 2019; Stephen et al., 2022). The importance of this question
157 has recently been highlighted in a scientific debate by multiple stakeholders with varying
158 interests, following a situational analysis on the roles and risks of wildlife in the emergence

159 of human infectious diseases (Kock and Caceres-Escobar, 2022). Unfortunately,
160 systematic evaluations that assess the effectiveness, efficacy, efficiency, acceptability,
161 usefulness, fairness, and sustainability of interventions in the context of their political and
162 community environments are exceptionally rare, yet they are fundamentally essential for
163 risk management (Wegner et al., 2022).

164 The second question – what are the individual, organizational or systems features
165 and processes that need to be in place to allow necessary changes to happen? – is the
166 concern of implementation science, which aims to systematically close the gap between
167 ‘what we know’ and ‘what we do’. The study of processes that translate research into
168 practice help us understand how contextual factors influence outcomes and to evaluate
169 the implementation of interventions (Nilsen 2020). It generates evidence to promote
170 interventions that enhance the uptake, sustainment, and scale-up of effective
171 interventions, or to replace ineffective ones.

172

Whereas the precautionary approach to zoonotic disease risk management can demand actions in the face of an ongoing risk, pressure to act should not distract attention to developing a strong evidentiary basis for risk management recommendations (Parkhurst, 2016; Herten and Bovenkerk, 2021).

173

174

175 Implementation science perspectives, models and frameworks must address three aims:
176 (1) describe and or guide the process of translating research into practice; (2) understand
177 and or explain what factors determine implementation outcomes; and (3) evaluate

178 implementation (Pfadenhauer et al., 2017). Different models and frameworks weigh or
179 emphasize these three aims to different extents.

180

181 **Process for drafting a framework for evaluating health intervention in wildlife trade**
182 **systems**

183 Our proposed framework was developed in an iterative manner (Figure 1). We
184 performed a narrative expert review, using a snowball approach to identifying literature
185 suitable to obtain a broad perspective on implementing and evaluating interventions in
186 complex health management settings. Table 1 provides a summary of the questions,
187 search criteria and results. Overall, we sought examples of published program
188 evaluations in the wildlife trade to identify shared aspects across existing frameworks and
189 propose adaptations for the wildlife trade. Two questions drove the review:

190 (A) Is there reason to believe that the shortage of evaluation and implementation
191 sciences regarding health risks in the wildlife trade has changed significantly since
192 the publications of Stephen et al. (Stephen et al., 2022)?

193 (B) Are there existing frameworks for implementation science – which includes
194 evaluation – for complex dynamic health interventions, regardless of the species
195 or circumstances?

196

197

198 **Figure 1.** Outline of the framework development process.

199

200 **Table1.** Summary of the questions and search criteria.

Question	Are there reasons to believe that the shortage of evaluation and implantation sciences regarding health risks in the wildlife trade changed significantly since the publications of Stephen et al. in 2022 (Stephen et al., 2022)?	Are there existing frameworks for implementation science (which includes evaluation) for complex dynamic health interventions, regardless of the species or circumstances?
Search type	Non-systematic, expert-based	Non-systematic, narrative review.
Keywords included into the search string	Evaluation, wildlife trade, health and risks	Complex, implementation science, evaluation, health, framework, model, theory
Database	Google Scholar, PubMed	Google Scholar, PubMed

Inclusion criteria	English-language reports or papers not identified by Stephen et al. (Stephen et al., 2022)	Frameworks that considered the knowledge-to-action lifecycle and were, in our opinion, adaptable to the wildlife trade setting
Exclusion criteria	Papers included in Stephen et al (Stephen et al., 2022)and paper not evaluating a risk reduction intervention.	Frameworks for knowledge-to-action for tame or liner problems
Comments	Members of the Evaluation Working Group of the Alliance Against Health Risks in the Wildlife Trade were asked to provide any papers or reports of program evaluations published between December 2001 to June 2023. Proposed key words for the experts to consider were based on Stephen et al (Stephen et al., 2022).	<p>We used a narrative review approach to find published models and frameworks that facilitate the translation of research findings into practice in complex health management settings.</p> <p>Damschroder (Damschroder et al., 2009) and Nilsen (Nilsen, 2020) became the starting points for our snowball search strategy.</p> <p>Reviewed terminology and constructs associated with the extracted frameworks, tried to standardize terminology, and find commonalities among the constructs in each framework and eliminated constructs that were not transferrable to a wildlife.</p> <p>Since narrative reviews do not aim to be inclusive of all literature, we</p>

		recognize that this may not include all relevant literature on a topic but rather give us an overview of common issues being discussed in the wildlife health surveillance community. 144 papers were read for this portion of the report.
--	--	---

201

202 **Results of the narrative expert review**

203

204 **Updates on the presence of evaluations of health interventions in wildlife trade**

205 We found no indication that the state of program evaluations had changed significantly
206 since the publication of Stephen et al. (Stephen et al., 2022). This agreed with the
207 International Union for Conservation of Nature 2022 situation analysis on the roles and
208 risks of wildlife in the emergence of human infectious diseases (Kock and Caceres-
209 Escobar, 2022).

210

“Existing literature has been inattentive to program implementation or evaluation studies. There was insufficient evidence to identify effective and sustainable risk management actions. Studies on the effects of social, epidemiological, and ecological context on intervention success were lacking as was research using a complex systems perspective.” (Stephen et al., 2022)

211

212

213 **Finding the guiding questions for the framework: origins and core components**

214 We couldn't find a framework specifically designed and validated to assess the success
215 or impact of wildlife trade health interventions. As a result, we had to draw on
216 implementation science frameworks that were created for use in complex human health
217 settings. Seven frameworks were chosen: SHIFT-evidence, PARIHS, RE-AIM,
218 PRECEDE-PROCEED, CFIR, PRISM, and the Knowledge-to-Action framework (Table
219 2). Each framework was reviewed and thematically clustered. Guiding questions were
220 aligned to generate an integrated list of considerations for the proposed wildlife trade
221 health risk implementation science framework (Table 3).

222 Three core questions were common across all seven frameworks: (1) Is there
223 evidence that the intervention could work? (2) What are the necessary processes and
224 steps to tailor an implementation strategy to the implementation context? and (3) was the
225 intervention successful and sustainable? For each core question, key questions, and
226 candidate subsidiary questions that help guide implementation, evaluation planning, and
227 assessments were identified by comparing shared, synergistic, or complementary
228 elements of the seven reviewed frameworks (Table 3).

229
230 **Table 2.** Brief introduction to seven intervention implementation frameworks used to
231 create the proposed wildlife trade risk implementation and evaluation framework.

Framework	Purpose	Brief description	Reference
Knowledge-to-Action framework	It is intended to help make knowledge translation sustainable,	A process model to help select implementation strategies. Based on a review of 31 planned action theories.	(Graham et al., 2006)

	valuable and evidence based.	Well suited to situations with a clearly defined set of recommendations about how you want someone to do something differently.	
Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR)	A framework to promote implementation theory development and verification about what works where and why across multiple contexts.	Considers five major domains: intervention characteristics, outer setting, inner setting, characteristics of the individuals involved and the process of implementation.	(Damschroder et al., 2009)
PRECEDE-PROCEED	Embodies two critical aspects of intervention, planning and evaluation.	A guide to help logically think about desired goals and work "backwards" to achieve that goal. Key attributes: (1) advances the ecological perspective on health, (2) remains population-centred, (3) demands democratic and participatory approaches, (4) sets the quality of life, rather than behaviour change or even health, as the goal and (5) is grounded in practice.	(Crosby and Noar, 2011; Porter, 2016)
RE-AIM	Used to plan, implement, evaluate, and sustain	RE-AIM stands for Reach, Effectiveness, Adoption, Implementation, and	(Gaglio et al., 2013)

	programs with contextual factors in mind	Maintenance. It was developed partially as a response to research conducted under optimal conditions instead of in real-world complex settings. It plans and assesses progress, reports results, and guides literature reviews.	
PARIHS	Outlines the determinants of successful implementation of evidence into practice with an emphasis on the context of an intervention's implementation	PARIHS stands for Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services. It emphasizes three interacting elements that influence the successful implementation of evidence-based practices: evidence, context, and facilitation. It is an impact or explanatory framework based on concept analyses and exploratory research.	(Stetler et al., 2011)
SHIFT-evidence	Provides three strategic principles and 12 rules to help navigate the process of change in complex systems	SHIFT stands for Successful Healthcare Improvements From Translating Evidence in complex systems. The framework is summarised by three strategic principles: (1)	(Reed et al., 2018, 2019)

		act scientifically and pragmatically, (2) embrace complexity, and (3) engage and empower.	
PRISM	Used to evaluate how an intervention interacts with the recipients to influence program adoption, implementation, maintenance, reach, and effectiveness.	PRISM stands for Practical Robust Implementation and Sustainability Model. It considers multilevel and dynamic interactions between the intervention, the characteristics of diverse recipients, the infrastructure for implementation and sustainability and other external factors.	(Feldstein and Glasgow, 2008)

232

233 **Table 3.** Shared question derived from common concerns and principles of the
 234 frameworks listed in Table 2 that could be used as prompts when designing program
 235 evaluations for health interventions in the wildlife trade. Modified or additional questions
 236 may be required to adapt to the specific circumstances of the program being evaluated.

Guiding question	Driving question	Subsidiary questions
Is there evidence that the intervention could work?	What is the social, cultural and or ecological problem?	Who cares about this situation and why? Who is asking for the intervention?
	Is there evidence for a plausible solution or intervention?	What are the determinants of the problem?

		Have reliable efficacy studies been undertaken?
	What circumstances, processes or conditions can affect the implementation of the proposed intervention?	<p>Is the intervention customizable?</p> <p>Have effectiveness studies been undertaken?</p> <p>Have likely barriers or enablers to successful program implementation been identified?</p> <p>How sensitive are the targeted outcomes to the conditions and context of intervention implementation?</p> <p>Does the planned intervention meet local needs and circumstances?</p>
What are the necessary processes and steps to tailor an implementation strategy to the context of implementation?	Has the local context been investigated and characterized in the context of the intervention?	<p>Has the social, epidemiological, and ecological context of the intervention been characterized?</p> <p>Have participatory methods been used to engage stakeholders in the design and implementation of the intervention?</p> <p>Has a situational assessment characterized the specific intervention setting's barriers and enablers to action?</p>
	Could the intervention work under the targeted situation and location?	<p>Is there capacity and readiness to implement the intervention?</p> <p>Have participatory methods found the intervention locally feasible, acceptable, ethical, and equitable?</p>

		<p>Has a policy review shown an enabling legislative framework to support the intervention?</p> <p>Has a resource assessment been undertaken?</p>
<p>To what extent was the implementation of the intervention successful and sustainable?</p>	<p>Were the intervention processes and procedures followed, and were the desired actions or behaviours adopted?</p>	<p>Has the process of implementation been monitored?</p> <p>Are there resources for monitoring?</p> <p>Has the fidelity to the program implementation been assessed?</p> <p>Who was reached by the intervention, and who did or did not participate?</p> <p>What facilitated implementation?</p> <p>Did an ongoing monitoring program track the process and fidelity of implementation and support adaptive management?</p>
	<p>What were the impacts?</p>	<p>Was an impact assessment done?</p> <p>Were the desired change targets reached?</p> <p>Is there evidence that health risks were reduced?</p> <p>What unanticipated effects occurred?</p>
	<p>Was it cost-effective?</p>	<p>Has an economic impact assessment or cost-benefit analysis been conducted?</p> <p>Were monetary and non-monetary costs and benefits considered?</p>

	Are ongoing actions needed?	<p>Are there monitoring programs in place to track the presence of risk determinants or desired health outcomes?</p> <p>Has an environmental or social assessment revealed the presence of ongoing risk factors?</p> <p>Have participatory methods provided consensus on intervention stopping points?</p>
	Can the desired effects be sustained?	<p>Does the change meet the ongoing needs of stakeholders?</p> <p>Is an adaptive management process in place?</p> <p>Are the required financial, non-financial and human resources available and sustainable?</p> <p>Can key implementation facilitators be sustained?</p>
What were the lessons learned?		

237

238 **Development of evidence-based risk reduction programs**

239 Several overarching issues must be considered when developing evidence-based risk
 240 reduction programs. The combination of the many questions that need to be considered
 241 when planning and implementing interventions and the complexity of wildlife trade begs
 242 the question of whether a single approach to program implementation or evaluation is
 243 desirable, reliable, and or appropriate. Notably, specific methods and transdisciplinary
 244 approaches must be tailored to the circumstances and context of the desired intervention.

245 **Understanding the social dimension**

246 A pathogen must overcome several hurdles before it can successfully invade, adapt and
247 survive in a new host. Social or sanitary barriers, e.g. biosecurity interventions as well as
248 the physical barriers of the host, e.g., skin and mucosa, must be overcome before a
249 spillover can happen. While we recognise that the individual and community immune
250 landscapes are complex and generally not well understood, we will focus here on the
251 equally important but heavily neglected social-cultural dimension in the fight against
252 pathogen spillover (Janes et al., 2012; Woldehanna and Zimicki, 2015).

253 When making health decisions, people are influenced by how the issue is
254 described (Gong et al., 2012). Factors such as age, gender and culture can influence the
255 perception, acceptance, and effectiveness of interventions. Thus, problem framing needs
256 to pay attention to stakeholders' worldviews, values, assumptions, and cultural models.
257 Social-cultural assessment must consider the community's sustainable problem-solving
258 capacity, strengths, resources, policy environment and readiness to change.

259

Sustainability is only achieved when stakeholders – both those operating the program and those served or affected by the intervention – are integral part of the planning, execution, and evaluation of the implementation effort, including defining the problem.

260

261

262 Program planning and implementation without agreement on the problem definition will
263 likely be of limited use (Milstein and Wetterhall, 1999). Epidemiological and ecological
264 studies can help uncover the determinants of the identified problems and help find factors

265 that predispose, reinforce, and enable the circumstances that cause risks to be
266 manifested and maintained. Modelling studies can simulate the impacts of interventions.
267 While such studies can reveal candidate targets for intervention, they need to be
268 accompanied by social sciences to determine if or how those affected by the intervention
269 recognize the problem.

270 It is generally advised to begin with a broad understanding and to refine it as more
271 information becomes available. Knowledge, Attitude and Practices (KAP) surveys provide
272 valuable access to quantitative and qualitative information that helps to reveal
273 misconceptions or misunderstandings. Multiple data-collection activities, such as
274 interviews with key opinion leaders, focus groups with community members,
275 observational data gathering, and surveys, are essential adjuncts to epidemiological data
276 when defining the problem. Techniques like mind mapping or systems thinking can help
277 to explore different aspects.

278

METHODOLOGICAL CASE STUDY
Social Assessment Social links can affect the effectiveness of interventions. From: Network analysis of a stakeholder community combating illegal wildlife trade (Moshier et al., 2019).
How was it done? The extent to which these stakeholders work and communicate amongst each other to improve the effectiveness or efficiency of a program was assessed using social network analysis and stakeholder interviews involving non-governmental, governmental and

academic groups. Participants were first identified using Google to find people working on combating illegal wildlife trade in the targeted geographic area. Initial contacts were asked for additional names to develop a list of participants. Participants were sent a questionnaire to determine how often they communicated with others, their means of communication and communication challenges. Responses were analysed using social network analysis software. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with a representative subset of participants to determine who they communicate with regarding illegal wildlife trade, and what kind of barriers exist to communications with their counterparts.

279

280 **Defining implementation success**

281 All aspects of planning and evaluation of an implemented intervention are predicated on
282 agreements on what constitutes success. Consequently, implementation success is
283 highly dependent on the ability and willingness of key stakeholders to act (Pfadenhauer
284 et al., 2017). A significant challenge in highly complex systems, like the trade of wildlife,
285 with its divergent values, ambiguities, and uncertainties, is a lack of clarity and agreement
286 on the definition, indicators, and thresholds for the success against which interventions
287 are judged. Moreover, these key parameters are fluent along the trade value chain and
288 generally absent in illegal trade operations, which by nature are not guided by interest
289 organisations of stakeholders (e.g. farmers' associations) nor are they regulated by law.

290 Definitions for intervention success differ. Cooke et al. for example proposed that
291 success happens when efforts are respectfully conducted, support partner-relevant
292 research that is accessible, understandable, and shared, and can create opportunities for

293 change (Cooke et al., 2020) where as Nutbeam suggested success exists when the
294 outcomes and change processes are valued (Nutbeam, 1998).

295

Outcomes that are defined mainly in terms of pathogen spillover or disease state, are not necessarily the same as the valued outcomes from all stakeholders' perspective. The same could be said when economic interests override how loss and potential gains are assessed. For example, activities that prevent pathogen spillover by excluding a species from the trade can at the same time eliminate an income stream essential for a community's food security.

296

297

298 In practice, programs must be cognizant of the intentions, values, and motivations of each
299 stakeholder and rights holder. By understanding these factors, programs can grasp the
300 diverse dimensions of success (Poulin et al., 2000). Since wildlife trade, even at the local
301 level, could carry pandemic risk potential, the question of the extent of stakeholder
302 involvement when the consequences are global is further complicated. Table 4 outlines
303 the essential outcomes to consider when evaluating the success of an implemented
304 intervention.

305

306 **Table 4.** Issues and questions that can inform a shared vision of success of a health
 307 intervention program in the wildlife trade, based on seven implementation frameworks
 308 described in Table 2.

Category	Was the implemented intervention...
Utility	...helpful to serve the information needs of intended users and appropriate to local conditions? ...realistic for the prevailing social, cultural, political, and environmental context?
Fidelity	...achieving its goals and objectives? ...operationalized as originally intended?
Acceptability	...acting with care and thought for the future? ...inclusive, ethical, unbiased, and frugal? ...legal and with due regard for the welfare of those involved and those affected by the program?
Cost-benefit	...efficiently using its fiscal, human, and other resources? ...producing value or benefits that exceed the cost of producing them? (cost-effectiveness) ...offsetting costs of interventions by the health, social and or ecological costs of non-intervention?
Effectiveness	... producing the desired results? ... reaching the necessary participants? ... producing technically adequate information about the features determining the worth or merit of the evaluated program? ... experiencing problems in implementation or sustainability?
Impact	... having acceptable impacts in terms of intended and unintended outcomes? ... causing unacceptable trade-offs or unintended negative impacts?

Sustainability	... scalable and transferable? ... empowering actors to maintain and sustain the intervention if it is needed?
Reproducibility	... repeatable? ... adaptable to changing circumstances? ... able to be more widely distributed?

309

310 The questions and variables used to define success depend on formal and informal risk
 311 management objectives and goals. Impacts could range from positive, measurable
 312 outcomes such as changes in practice, disease rates, or pathogen detection frequency
 313 to constructivist outcomes like improved participant self-efficacy, increased trust in
 314 program deliverers, or changes in social norms. They can range from local impacts (e.g.,
 315 changes in practice at one local marketplace) to national or even international changes,
 316 e.g., in policy (Douthwaite et al., 2003). It is important to understand success as a
 317 multifactorial dimension. It includes pre-implementation success (e.g. contribution to
 318 knowledge, partnership and relationship building), proximate achievements (e.g.,
 319 changes in a policy or practice) and ultimate successes (e.g., improved health, economic,
 320 welfare and environmental security) (Cooke et al., 2020).

321

322 **Measuring success**

323 It seems unreasonable – in most cases – to assume a simple causal chain linking a risk
 324 reduction intervention to the success of an implementation strategy. However, evaluators
 325 and planners will want to know whether the objectives and outcomes of the intervention
 326 have been achieved and whether and how this achievement can be attributed to the
 327 intervention. Key to our proposed framework is the recognition that a complete evaluation

328 of a particular risk factor associated with specific adverse health outcomes requires
329 consideration of other determinants of those outcomes, as well as interactions between
330 the risk factor of interest and these determinants (Krewski et al., 2014). It also requires
331 an evaluation of the implementation process and practices.

332 Tools that foster inter-sectoral collaboration such as National-Bridging Workshops
333 (Belot et al., 2021), operated with logic models, influence diagrams, and participatory
334 mapping help to look at the relationship between the intervention and the systems to
335 better inventory the possible suite of health, economic social, and environmental impacts.

336 While we can define evidence-based indicators to document a change, the
337 threshold for acceptability will most often need to be negotiated due to the varied values
338 and expectations within the complex, dynamic wildlife trade. Evidence-based selection
339 criteria for indicators can improve the transparency, relevance, and robustness of
340 program implementation and evaluation. However, consultative processes need to be
341 undertaken to negotiate with stakeholders the thresholds of success that would enhance
342 program acceptance and compliance.

343 Epidemiological studies can be used to establish an association between
344 interventions and changes in health outcomes. Stephen et al. (2022) found that most
345 examples of evaluations of interventions addressing health risks in wildlife were case
346 reports and case series (which tell us about the possibility of an association between an
347 observed effect and a specific environmental exposure) and cross-sectional study
348 designs (which measure the risk factor and outcome at the same time, but do not tell us
349 about their relationship, especially whether it is a causal one). However, case series and
350 cross-sectional designs are best used for hypothesis generation, not for proving cause-

351 effect relationships. Challenges in conducting epidemiological studies in wildlife trade are
352 well known and limit the ability to meet the standards of evidence usually required to
353 document the effects of an intervention. Example problems include lack of access to
354 wildlife – particularly those involved in the illegal trade – and the limited ability to obtain
355 representative population samples, problems in identifying or maintaining control
356 populations, competing utilisation of wildlife as food, the co-occurrence of multiple
357 interventions at the same time, lack of validated diagnostic tests, and limits in the capacity
358 for standard analytical techniques to account for complex, dynamic systems. Such
359 challenges often necessitate using mixed models and participatory approaches to
360 triangulate towards a pragmatic agreement of cause-effect relationships (Shury and
361 Jardine, 2022).

362

Epidemiological methods have started incorporating techniques like agent-based modelling to better capture the complexity of epidemiological systems. However, mathematical models are only as accurate as the data they are based on. Challenges such as model design, data accessibility and sharing, the reliance on multiple assumptions in systems-based models, and the identification of interactions and interrelationships continue to exist (Galea et al., 2010; Cerdá and Keyes, 2019).

363

364

365 In complex systems like wildlife trade health risks, tensions may arise between scientific
366 rigour, quantifiable outcomes, and qualitative assessments. Standardising evaluation
367 techniques may hinder adaptation to local contexts. A solely mechanistic biomedical

368 framework neglects social and ecological factors, creating an imbalance in intervention
369 evaluation and success perception.

370 An integrated or cumulative effects environmental health assessment is the third
371 phase of modern environmental risk management (Lebret, 2016). These are becoming
372 commonplace in other sectors as they provide descriptions of multiple impacts from
373 multiple stressors so that they can be evaluated against the potential societal benefits of
374 the causes of the stressors. Research and development of such methods to support
375 evidence-based design and evaluation are critically needed for wildlife trade. Since our
376 proposed framework requires attention to a wider suite of mechanisms to assess the
377 implementation of a risk reduction intervention, it will most likely be beyond the scope of
378 one organization and sector to fulfil all requirements for a comprehensive scope of
379 activity, especially when public and private interests intersect. In this regard, individuals
380 and organizations from all sectors with clear leadership positions and careful attention to
381 the roles and responsibilities of the various players influencing health determinants and
382 outcomes are needed.

383

384 **Understand context**

385 The seven frameworks in Table 2 consistently emphasize that context matters. Context
386 is taken to mean anything internal or external to the intervention that may act as a barrier
387 or facilitator to its implementation or effects. The success of a complex intervention is
388 highly dependent on context. An effective intervention in some settings could be
389 ineffective or harmful elsewhere.

390

"Understanding how interventions relate to context is critical to understanding how they work; why they sometimes fail; whether they can be successfully adapted, scaled up or translated from one context to another; why their impacts vary; and how far effects observed in one context can be generalized to others" (Craig et al., 2018).

391

392

393 Wildlife trade interventions are social practices created, delivered, adapted and
394 experienced by people who influence and are influenced by the circumstances in which
395 they live. These social influences range from the hyper-local (e.g., the way a trapper holds
396 his/her animals) to effects felt from vast geographical distances (e.g., decisions of urban
397 dwellers to purchase wildlife products sourced some distance away). Well-established
398 theories of change, such as the Health Belief Model (Abraham and Sheeran, 2015) and
399 the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Bosnjak et al., 2020), emphasize the role of individual
400 characteristics (i.e., perceptions, attitudes, interests, and priorities) and the social
401 environment (i.e. policies, resources, social norms, and power dynamics) as key to
402 whether people adopt a new behaviour.

403 An initial step in evaluating the relationship between context and intervention
404 outcomes involves defining the scope of the intervention using methods like participatory
405 mapping, focus groups, policy analysis, or situational analysis. Yet not all contextual
406 factors affect all interventions. Context assessments must be tailored to local
407 circumstances and the specific intervention with which they interact. The Context and
408 Implementation of Complex Interventions (CICI) framework focuses on the assessment
409 of factors that: (i) influence the intervention, its implementation, its population reach and

410 its effectiveness; (ii) exert influence on the intervention, its implementation and its
411 outcomes and (iii) interact with other domains of context (Pfadenhauer et al., 2017).

412 In 2018, Craig et al. proposed realist evaluation, process evaluation and causal
413 modelling as methods to better understand the relationship between context and
414 implementation outcomes (Craig et al., 2018).

415

METHODOLOGICAL CASE STUDY
<p>Context Assessment</p> <p>Stakeholder selection matters when trying to characterize the context of zoonoses control programs.</p> <p>From: Tackling wicked problems in infection prevention and control: a guideline for co-creation with stakeholders (Woezik et al., 2016).</p>
<p>How was it done?</p> <p>Step-by-step guidelines were developed for stakeholder involvement and co-creation when tackling zoonoses control programs. This involved six steps: (1) Create a list of candidate stakeholders by conducting a literature scan to get acquainted with its problem definitions, solutions, and (key) stakeholder; (2) Involve at least two field experts to validate the list of candidates and provide locally relevant practical insights; (3) use snowball sampling by asking relevant candidates to identify other candidates; (4) shorten the list of candidates by asking stakeholders to rank the candidates to find out which are perceived as key stakeholders; (5) use interviews or focus groups with key stakeholders with different backgrounds and hierarchical positions to understand their values, needs, and perspectives on the problem; (6) validate stakeholders' key</p>

values by sending a survey to all involved stakeholders. This guideline provides the evaluator with a systematic, transparent approach to assembling stakeholders who can help assess the impacts of context on the implementation and impacts of a program.

416

417 **Evaluate the implementation process**

418 A process evaluation considers the degree to which an intervention was delivered as
419 intended, whether the intervention reached the intended participants, how the intervention
420 led to the observed changes, and how the context affects the implementation and
421 outcomes (Skivington et al., 2021). Process evaluations examine the relationship
422 between the intervention and its components, with context and outcome. They help
423 distinguish between implementation failure (where the intervention is poorly delivered)
424 and failures of the intervention itself (Grant et al., 2020). Examples of implementation
425 failure include poor study design combined with declining stakeholder motivation and
426 resource constraints, weak law enforcement and or political support that prevents the
427 implementation from achieving its goals. On the other hand, an intervention may fail if it
428 is well implemented but does not achieve its objectives.

429 Process evaluations depend on a system for monitoring the program's
430 implementation process and benefit from having an implementation logic model that
431 specifies the intended process. Process evaluations frequently rely on multiple methods.
432 While some process indicators, such as the number of available personnel, use of
433 resources, and costs, can be quantified, others require qualitative approaches, such as
434 those involving implementation barriers, facilitators, and acceptability. Being locally
435 contextually relevant will necessitate including tacit and local knowledge. Participatory

436 action research may be used to gain insights from stakeholders on questions such as
437 how the intervention was intended to be undertaken, what impeded or facilitated its
438 implementation, who and how many people or institutions did or did not participate, and
439 how evidence to support the action was shared, received, and trusted.

440 Selection of the most appropriate methods demands that evaluators have a sufficient
441 understanding of the possible impacts of the program actions, building from a good
442 understanding of the core tasks, populations, threats, and hazards that need to be
443 managed.

444 Process evaluation must be a continuous process from the beginning of the
445 interventions onwards. It supports evidence-based adaptive management which
446 “increase the ability to fashion timely responses in the face of new information and a
447 setting of varied stakeholder objectives and preferences” (National_Research_Council,
448 2004).

449

Adaptive management requires collaborations to characterize the full extent of a
problem, anticipate the possible consequences of responses throughout the system
being managed, evaluate the impacts of interventions, and incorporate lessons
learned into future decisions (Ebi, 2017).

450

451

METHODOLOGICAL CASE STUDY

Process Evaluation

Exploring how implementation processes are linked to the surveillance outcomes.

From: Mechanisms and Contextual Factors Affecting the Implementation of Animal Health Surveillance in Tanzania: A Process Evaluation (George et al., 2022).

How was it done?

The study design was guided by a framework for process evaluation of complex interventions developed by Moore et al. (Moore et al., 2015), adapted to understand the relationships between animal health surveillance implementation, mechanisms and context. Data were collected to assess; (1) whether the surveillance program was delivered as per guidelines(fidelity); (2) number of surveillance reports submitted on time (adherence); (3) proportion of the intended participants who took part in the program (participation); (4) extent of level of participation in surveillance activities (exposure); (5) stakeholder satisfaction with the delivery of the program (satisfaction); and (6) information on social, physical or political features that influenced the implementation of the program (context). Information was gathered through questionnaires, key informant interviews, records reviews and observations. Participants were randomly and purposively sampled based on their role in animal health surveillance and designations at their respective institutions. Due to limited resources, evaluators selected three districts as surrogates for national representatives.

452

453

454 **Assessment of the evidence**

455 Decision makers want resource-saving recommendations based on the best evidence.
456 Yet, there is no single, widely accepted explicit criterion on what constitutes 'best'
457 evidence, how conflicting evidence could be weighed and assessed, or the standards of
458 quality required to accept or reject evidence. There are differences in opinion about what
459 represents good evidence as well as the breadth of evidence needed before acting.
460 Politicians, economists and budget managers, the target population, academic
461 researchers, government regulators and practitioners can have varying expectations for
462 the types and quality of information needed to support decisions. These different
463 perspectives are reflected in the wide range of methods and measures used to establish
464 program effectiveness.

465 There are some high-level guidelines for assessing different types of evidence. For
466 example, Baba and Hakem Zadeh (2012) claim that evidence is strong when (i) it fits the
467 decision context, (ii) its methods of production and analysis are transparent, (iii) it includes
468 more contextual information, (iv) its method of production can be replicated, and (v) there
469 is consensus (or near-consensus) about the evidence across all stakeholders. Evidence
470 can be deemed 'good' if it is from investigations that are convincingly designed and
471 interpreted, are supported by information from within and outside the project and are
472 trusted enough to help us understand what happened in the past or plan for what to do in
473 the future (Fossey et al., 2002).

474 Pragmatic approaches to assessing evidence value the legitimacy of solving a
475 problem in one circumstance without the need to prove it has broader applicability
476 (Stephen et al., 2016).

For complex ecohealth issues, evaluators might ask if the evaluation was (1) "undertaken in the setting where results will be applied under conditions experienced by the populations of concern; (2) strives to inspire effective, ethical, and sustainable actions in 'real-world' settings to address complex problems important to people in those settings, rather than discover underlying mechanisms of causation; (3) focuses on accelerating the integration of research with policy" (Stephen et al., 2016).

477

478

479 There are guidelines for assessing evidence in research studies such as the
480 Checklist for One Health Epidemiological Reporting of Evidence (Davis et al., 2017) and
481 the Meta Quality Appraisal Tool (Rosella et al., 2016), along with many developed for
482 qualitative health research (Majid and Vanstone, 2018). Yet, this short list of examples is
483 biased towards standards used in the public health realm as opposed to legal standards
484 for evidence, or standards used in economics or traditional knowledge systems. Given
485 that biomedical evidence is not the only evidence needed for evidence-based decision
486 making, conversations amongst project partners and stakeholders on what types and
487 quality of evidence they need is a critical foundation of evidence-based risk management.
488 Stakeholders' perceptions of the quality and validity of evidence will impact their trust and
489 willingness to be part of the intervention (Damschroder et al., 2009). There must be an
490 agreed standard for the nature of biological, ecological, and social evidence to be
491 considered when making decisions and how to accommodate varying levels of reliability,
492 validity, uncertainty, and representativeness of the evidence being considered.

493 Practitioners and researchers will often need to rely on evidence triangulation. This
494 is the process of using more than one approach to researching a question to increase

495 confidence in the findings through confirmation using two or more independent measures
496 (Heale and Forbes, 2013). Triangulation can result in three outcomes: (1) the results
497 may converge, (2) the results may be complementary to each other, or (3) the results
498 may be divergent or contradictory. Convergence increases validity through verification,
499 while complementarity highlights different aspects of the issue under study. Divergence,
500 in contrast, asks for new and better explanations.

501 Plans to evaluate and weigh evidence are faced with three dilemmas. First, how
502 to weigh evidence that supports management of risk factors of wildlife trade origin with
503 evidence about impacts on the fitness and long-term viability of wild or domestic animal
504 populations or on human health and economies? Second, how is the precautionary
505 approach applied in evidence evaluation and use? Third, how can we address the
506 prevailing scientific uncertainty or ongoing debates regarding the individual or cumulative
507 impacts of wildlife trade-related risk factors?

508 Rules developed through partnerships and consultations must guide how to deal
509 with uncertain or conflicting evidence and provide criteria for establishing causal
510 relationships. Lack of such rules can lead to conflict and misunderstandings on the
511 quality, meaning, reliability or utility of the body of evidence upon which to make
512 recommendations. Without agreement on such terms, there is no standard way for a
513 group to derive a shared interpretation of the utility or effectiveness of an intervention.

514

515 **Conclusion**

516 Interventions in wildlife trade must be effective and therefore evidence based. Our guiding
517 document and the proposed framework should be seen as a starting point. Wildlife trade

518 is by nature a complex system with multiple stakeholders, some of which are not
519 accessible, e.g., in the case of illegal trade. Although wildlife is a constant source of
520 pathogens with epidemic and pandemic potential, epidemics and pandemics are
521 generally driven by farmed animals and humans. Independent of our personal worldview,
522 we must recognise that many stakeholders make a living out of the trade of wild animals,
523 which calls for alternatives to secure livelihoods and complicates a global ban on wildlife
524 trade. It is important to find a balance between the necessary use of wildlife and its
525 exploitation for trade values and the associated health risks for humans, animals and the
526 environment. Lastly, we need to accept that complex systems are prone to conflicts of
527 interest which require moderation and transparency.

528

529 **Acknowledgments**

530 We thank the International Alliance Against Health Risks in Wildlife Trade for its focus on
531 this topic and its encouragement and support to produce this report. We acknowledge the
532 efforts of the Evaluation Working Group of the Alliance, which used the experience and
533 networks of its members to search for example of validated program evaluations in the
534 wildlife trade.

535

536 **References**

537 Abdullah, A., A. Ardiansyah, M. Balestri, M. Campera, J. Chavez, T. Dewi, A. Fourage,
538 E.L. Hankinson, K. Hedger, B. Leupen, S. Manson, T.Q. Morcatty, K.A.I. Nekarlis, V.
539 Nijman, P.E.R. Pereyra, E. Sintya, M.S. Svensson, and M. Xie, 2024: Parrot trade and

540 the potential risk of psittacosis as a zoonotic disease in Indonesian bird markets. *Birds*
541 **5**, 137–154, DOI: 10.3390/birds5010010.

542 Abraham, C., and P. Sheeran, 2015: The health belief model, pp. 30–55. In: Conner, M.,
543 and P. Norman (eds). Berkshire, UK: Open University Press.

544 Arias, M., A. Hinsley, and E.J. Milner-Gulland, 2021: Use of evidence for decision-making
545 by conservation practitioners in the illegal wildlife trade. *People Nat.* **3**, 1110–1126,
546 DOI: 10.1002/pan3.10258.

547 Belot, G., F. Caya, K.M. Errecaborde, T. Traore, B. Lafia, A. Skrypnyk, D. Montabond, M.
548 Carron, S. Corning, R. Sreedharan, N. Isla, T. Schmidt, G. Gongal, D. Samhour, E.
549 Perez-Gutierrez, A. Riviere-Cinnamond, J. Xing, S. Chungong, and S. de la Rocque,
550 2021: IHR-PVS National Bridging Workshops, a tool to operationalize the collaboration
551 between human and animal health while advancing sector-specific goals in countries.
552 *Plos One* **16**, e0245312, DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0245312.

553 Bosnjak, M., I. Ajzen, and P. Schmidt, 2020: The Theory of Planned Behavior: Selected
554 Recent Advances and Applications. *Eur.'s J. Psychol.* **16**, 352–356, DOI:
555 10.5964/ejop.v16i3.3107.

556 Braithwaite, J., K. Churruca, J.C. Long, L.A. Ellis, and J. Herkes, 2018: When complexity
557 science meets implementation science: a theoretical and empirical analysis of systems
558 change. *BMC Med.* **16**, 63, DOI: 10.1186/s12916-018-1057-z.

559 Cerdá, M., and K.M. Keyes, 2019: Systems modeling to advance the promise of data
560 science in epidemiology. *Am. J. Epidemiology* **188**, 862–865, DOI:
561 10.1093/aje/kwy262.

562 Cheng, S., J. Robinson, N. Cox, A. Olsson, D. Biggs, M. Mascia, and M. McKinnon, 2017:
563 Mapping the evidence: Effectiveness of international wildlife trade practices and
564 policies. Conservation International, Working Paper #1,
565 [https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318725745_Mapping_the_Evidence_Effecti](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318725745_Mapping_the_Evidence_Effectiveness_of_International_Wildlife_Trade_Practices_and_Policies)
566 [veness_of_International_Wildlife_Trade_Practices_and_Policies](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318725745_Mapping_the_Evidence_Effectiveness_of_International_Wildlife_Trade_Practices_and_Policies).

567 Cooke, S.J., T. Rytwinski, J.J. Taylor, E.A. Nyboer, V.M. Nguyen, J.R. Bennett, N. Young,
568 S. Aitken, G. Auld, J.-F. Lane, K.A. Prior, K.E. Smokorowski, P.A. Smith, A.L. Jacob,
569 D.R. Browne, J.M. Blais, J.T. Kerr, B. Ormeci, S.M. Alexander, C.R. Burn, R.T. Buxton,
570 D.M. Orihel, J.C. Vermaire, D.L. Murray, P. Simon, K.A. Edwards, J. Clarke, M.A.
571 Xenopoulos, I. Gregory-Eaves, E.M. Bennett, and J.P. Smol, 2020: On “success” in
572 applied environmental research — What is it, how can it be achieved, and how does
573 one know when it has been achieved? *Environ. Rev.* **28**, 357–372, DOI: 10.1139/er-
574 2020-0045.

575 Craig, P., E.D. Ruggiero, K.L. Frohlich, E. Mykhalovskiy, M. White, R. Campbell, S.
576 Cummins, N. Edwards, K. Hunt, F. Kee, C. Loppie, L. Moore, D. Ogilvie, M. Petticrew,
577 B. Poland, V. Ridde, J. Shoveller, S. Viehbeck, and D. Wight, 2018: Taking account of
578 context in population health intervention research: guidance for producers, users and
579 funders of research. DOI: 10.3310/cihr-nihr-01.

580 Crosby, R., and S.M. Noar, 2011: What is a planning model? An introduction to
581 PRECEDE-PROCEED. *J. Public Heal. Dent.* **71**, S7–S15, DOI: 10.1111/j.1752-
582 7325.2011.00235.x.

583 Damschroder, L.J., D.C. Aron, R.E. Keith, S.R. Kirsh, J.A. Alexander, and J.C. Lowery,
584 2009: Fostering implementation of health services research findings into practice: a
585 consolidated framework for advancing implementation science. *Implement. Sci.* **4**, 50,
586 DOI: 10.1186/1748-5908-4-50.

587 Davis, M.F., S.C. Rankin, J.M. Schurer, S. Cole, L. Conti, P. Rabinowitz, C.E.R. Group,
588 G. Gray, L. Kahn, C. Machalaba, J. Mazet, M. Pappaioanou, J. Sargeant, A.
589 Thompson, S. Weese, and J. Zinnstag, 2017: Checklist for One Health Epidemiological
590 Reporting of Evidence (COHERE). *One Heal.* **4**, 14–21, DOI:
591 10.1016/j.onehlt.2017.07.001.

592 Diseases, T.L.I., 2003: Trade in wild animals: a disaster ignored. *Lancet Infect. Dis.* **3**,
593 391–391, DOI: 10.1016/s1473-3099(03)00695-9.

594 Douthwaite, B., T. Kuby, E. van de Fliert, and S. Schulz, 2003: Impact pathway evaluation:
595 an approach for achieving and attributing impact in complex systems. *Agric. Syst.* **78**,
596 243–265, DOI: 10.1016/s0308-521x(03)00128-8.

597 Ebi, K., 2017: Climate Change And Health Risks: Assessing And Responding To Them
598 Through ‘Adaptive Management.’ *Heal. Aff.* **30**, 924–930, DOI:
599 10.1377/hlthaff.2011.0071.

600 Feldstein, A.C., and R.E. Glasgow, 2008: A practical, robust implementation and
601 sustainability model (PRISM) for integrating research findings into practice. *Jt. Comm.*
602 *J. Qual. patient Saf.* **34**, 228–43, DOI: 10.1016/s1553-7250(08)34030-6.

603 Fossey, E., C. Harvey, F. Mcdermott, and L. Davidson, 2002: Understanding and
604 Evaluating Qualitative Research*. *Aust. N. Zealand J. Psychiatry* **36**, 717–732, DOI:
605 10.1046/j.1440-1614.2002.01100.x.

606 Gaglio, B., J.A. Shoup, and R.E. Glasgow, 2013: The RE-AIM framework: a systematic
607 review of use over time. *Am. J. public Heal.* **103**, e38-46, DOI:
608 10.2105/ajph.2013.301299.

609 Galea, S., M. Riddle, and G.A. Kaplan, 2010: Causal thinking and complex system
610 approaches in epidemiology. *Int. J. Epidemiology* **39**, 97–106, DOI:
611 10.1093/ije/dyp296.

612 George, J., B. Häsler, E.V.G. Komba, M. Rweyemamu, S.I. Kimera, and J.E.D. Mlangwa,
613 2022: Mechanisms and Contextual Factors Affecting the Implementation of Animal
614 Health Surveillance in Tanzania: A Process Evaluation. *Frontiers Vet Sci* **8**, 790035,
615 DOI: 10.3389/fvets.2021.790035.

616 Gong, J., Y. Zhang, J. Feng, Y. Huang, Y. Wei, and W. Zhang, 2012: Influence of framing
617 on medical decision making. *EXCLI J.* **12**, 20–9.

618 Graham, I.D., J. Logan, M.B. Harrison, S.E. Straus, J. Tetroe, W. Caswell, and N.
619 Robinson, 2006: Lost in knowledge translation: Time for a map? *J. Contin. Educ. Heal.*
620 *Prof.* **26**, 13–24, DOI: 10.1002/chp.47.

621 Grant, A., C. Bugge, and M. Wells, 2020: Designing process evaluations using case study
622 to explore the context of complex interventions evaluated in trials. *Trials* **21**, 982, DOI:
623 10.1186/s13063-020-04880-4.

624 Heale, R., and D. Forbes, 2013: Understanding triangulation in research. *Évid. Based*
625 *Nurs.* **16**, 98–98, DOI: 10.1136/eb-2013-101494.

626 Herten, J. van, and B. Bovenkerk, 2021: The precautionary principle in zoonotic disease
627 control. *Public Heal. Ethics* **14**, 180–190, DOI: 10.1093/phe/phab012.

628 Hilderink, M.H., and I.I. de Winter, 2021: No need to beat around the bushmeat – The
629 role of wildlife trade and conservation initiatives in the emergence of zoonotic diseases.
630 *Heliyon* **7**, e07692, DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e07692.

631 IPBES, 2020: IPBES workshop on biodiversity and pandemics pp. 1–18.
632 Intergovernmental Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, Bonn, Germany.

633 Janes, C.R., K.K. Corbett, J.H. Jones, and J. Trostle, 2012: Emerging infectious diseases:
634 the role of social sciences. *Lancet* **380**, 1884–1886, DOI: 10.1016/s0140-
635 6736(12)61725-5.

636 Karesh, W.B., R.A. Cook, E.L. Bennett, and J. Newcomb, 2005: Wildlife trade and global
637 disease emergence. *Emerg Infect Dis* **11**, 1000–1002, DOI: 10.3201/eid1107.050194.

638 Karesh, W.B., A. Dobson, J.O. Lloyd-Smith, J. Lubroth, M.A. Dixon, M. Bennett, S.
639 Aldrich, T. Harrington, P. Formenty, E.H. Loh, C.C. Machalaba, M.J. Thomas, and D.L.
640 Heymann, 2012: Ecology of zoonoses: natural and unnatural histories. *Lancet* **380**,
641 1936–1945, DOI: 10.1016/s0140-6736(12)61678-x.

642 Kock, R., and H. Caceres-Escobar, 2022: Situation analysis on the roles and risks of
643 wildlife in the emergence of human infectious diseases pp. 1–136. IUCN, Gland,
644 Switzerland.

645 Krewski, D., M. Westphal, M.E. Andersen, G.M. Paoli, W.A. Chiu, M. Al-Zoughool, M.C.
646 Croteau, L.D. Burgoon, and I. Cote, 2014: A framework for the next generation of risk
647 science. *Environ. Heal. Perspect.* **122**, 796–805, DOI: 10.1289/ehp.1307260.

648 Lebret, E., 2016: Integrated environmental health impact assessment for risk Governance
649 purposes: Across what do we integrate? *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Heal.* **13**, 71, DOI:
650 10.3390/ijerph13010071.

651 Lockwood, C., M. Stephenson, L. Lizarondo, J. van D. Hoek, and M. Harrison, 2016:
652 Evidence implementation: Development of an online methodology from the
653 knowledge-to-action model of knowledge translation. *Int. J. Nurs. Pr.* **22**, 322–329,
654 DOI: 10.1111/ijn.12469.

655 Majid, U., and M. Vanstone, 2018: Appraising qualitative research for evidence
656 syntheses: A compendium of quality appraisal tools. *Qual. Heal. Res.* **28**, 2115–2131,
657 DOI: 10.1177/1049732318785358.

658 McBride, D.S., S.K. Garushyants, J. Franks, A.F. Magee, S.H. Overend, D. Huey, A.M.
659 Williams, S.A. Faith, A. Kandeil, S. Trifkovic, L. Miller, T. Jeevan, A. Patel, J.M. Nolting,
660 M.J. Tonkovich, J.T. Genders, A.J. Montoney, K. Kasnyik, T.J. Linder, S.N. Bevins,
661 J.B. Lenocho, J.C. Chandler, T.J. DeLiberto, E.V. Koonin, M.A. Suchard, P. Lemey, R.J.
662 Webby, M.I. Nelson, and A.S. Bowman, 2023: Accelerated evolution of SARS-CoV-2
663 in free-ranging white-tailed deer. *Nat. Commun.* **14**, 5105, DOI: 10.1038/s41467-023-
664 40706-y.

665 Milstein, R.L., and S.F. Wetterhall, 1999: Framework for program evaluation in public
666 health. *MMWR Recomm. Rep. : Morb. Mortal. Wkly. Rep. Recomm. Rep.* **48**, 1–40.

667 Moore, G.F., S. Audrey, M. Barker, L. Bond, C. Bonell, W. Hardeman, L. Moore, A.
668 O’Cathain, T. Tinati, D. Wight, and J. Baird, 2015: Process evaluation of complex
669 interventions: Medical Research Council guidance. *BMJ : Br. Méd. J.* **350**, h1258, DOI:
670 10.1136/bmj.h1258.

671 Moshier, A., J. Steadman, and D.L. Roberts, 2019: Network analysis of a stakeholder
672 community combatting illegal wildlife trade. *Conserv. Biol.* **33**, 1307–1317, DOI:
673 10.1111/cobi.13336.

674 National Research Council, 2004: Case studies of adaptive management, pp. 52–82. In:
675 Adaptive Management for Water Resources Project Planning. Washington D.C., USA:
676 The National Academic Press.

677 Nilsen, P., 2020: Overview of theories, models and frameworks in implementation
678 science, pp. 8–31. In: Handbook on Implementation Science. Edward Elgar Publishing.

679 Nutbeam, D., 1998: Evaluating health promotion — Progress, problems and solutions.
680 *Heal. Promot. Int.* **13**, 27–44, DOI: 10.1093/heapro/13.1.27.

681 O.H.H.L.E.P., W. Markotter, T.C. Mettenleiter, W.B. Adisasmito, S. Almuhairi, C.B.
682 Behraves, P. Bilivogui, S.A. Bukachi, N. Casas, N.C. Becerra, D.F. Charron, A.
683 Chaudhary, J.R.C. Zanella, A.A. Cunningham, O. Dar, N. Debnath, B. Dungu, E.
684 Farag, G.F. Gao, D.T.S. Hayman, M. Khaita, M.P.G. Koopmans, C. Machalaba, J.S.
685 Mackenzie, S. Morand, V. Smolenskiy, and L. Zhou, 2023: Prevention of zoonotic
686 spillover: From relying on response to reducing the risk at source. *PLOS Pathog.* **19**,
687 e1011504, DOI: 10.1371/journal.ppat.1011504.

688 Parkhurst, J.O., 2016: Appeals to evidence for the resolution of wicked problems: the
689 origins and mechanisms of evidentiary bias. *Polic. Sci.* **49**, 373–393, DOI:
690 10.1007/s11077-016-9263-z.

691 Pfadenhauer, L.M., A. Gerhardus, K. Mozygemba, K.B. Lysdahl, A. Booth, B. Hofmann,
692 P. Wahlster, S. Polus, J. Burns, L. Brereton, and E. Rehfuss, 2017: Making sense of
693 complexity in context and implementation: the Context and Implementation of Complex
694 Interventions (CICI) framework. *Implement. Sci.* : **12**, 21, DOI: 10.1186/s13012-017-
695 0552-5.

696 Porter, C.M., 2016: Revisiting Precede–Proceed: A leading model for ecological and
697 ethical health promotion. *Heal. Educ. J.* **75**, 753–764, DOI:
698 10.1177/0017896915619645.

699 Poulin, M.E., P.W. Harris, and P.R. Jones, 2000: The Significance of Definitions of
700 Success in Program Evaluation. *Eval. Rev.* **24**, 516–536, DOI:
701 10.1177/0193841x0002400504.

702 Reed, J.E., S. Green, and C. Howe, 2019: Translating evidence in complex systems: a
703 comparative review of implementation and improvement frameworks. *Int. J. Qual.*
704 *Heal. Care* **31**, 173–182, DOI: 10.1093/intqhc/mzy158.

705 Reed, J.E., C. Howe, C. Doyle, and D. Bell, 2018: Simple rules for evidence translation
706 in complex systems: A qualitative study. *BMC Med.* **16**, 92, DOI: 10.1186/s12916-018-
707 1076-9.

708 Rosella, L., C. Bowman, B. Pach, S. Morgan, T. Fitzpatrick, and V. Goel, 2016: The
709 development and validation of a meta-tool for quality appraisal of public health
710 evidence: Meta Quality Appraisal Tool (MetaQAT). *Public Heal.* **136**, 57–65, DOI:
711 10.1016/j.puhe.2015.10.027.

712 Sas-Rolfes, M. 't, D.W.S. Challender, A. Hinsley, D. Veríssimo, and E.J. Milner-Gulland,
713 2019: Illegal wildlife trade: Patterns, processes, and governance. *Annu. Rev. Environ.*
714 *Resour.* **44**, 1–28, DOI: 10.1146/annurev-environ-101718-033253.

715 Shury, T., and C. Jardine, 2022: Wildlife Population Health. 37–48, DOI: 10.1007/978-3-
716 030-90510-1_4.

717 Skivington, K., L. Matthews, S.A. Simpson, P. Craig, J. Baird, J.M. Blazeby, K.A. Boyd,
718 N. Craig, D.P. French, E. McIntosh, M. Petticrew, J. Rycroft-Malone, M. White, and L.

719 Moore, 2021: A new framework for developing and evaluating complex interventions:
720 update of Medical Research Council guidance. *BMJ* **374**, n2061, DOI:
721 10.1136/bmj.n2061.

722 Stephen, C., T. Burns, and A. Riviere-Cinamond, 2016: Pragmatism (or realism) in
723 research: Is there an ecohealth scope of practice? *EcoHealth* **13**, 230–233, DOI:
724 10.1007/s10393-016-1125-9.

725 Stephen, C., L.P. Carmo, D. de las N.M. Valle, B. Friker, F.M. Sousa, B. Vidondo, and J.
726 Berezowski, 2022: The implementation gap in emerging disease risk management in
727 the wildlife trade. *J. Wildl. Dis.* **58**, 705–715, DOI: 10.7589/jwd-d-21-00199.

728 Stetler, C.B., L.J. Damschroder, C.D. Helfrich, and H.J. Hagedorn, 2011: A guide for
729 applying a revised version of the PARIHS framework for implementation. *Implement.*
730 *Sci.* **6**, 99–99, DOI: 10.1186/1748-5908-6-99.

731 Thomas-Walters, L., D. Veríssimo, E. Gadsby, D. Roberts, and R.J. Smith, 2020: Taking
732 a more nuanced look at behavior change for demand reduction in the illegal wildlife
733 trade. *Conserv. Sci. Pr.* **2**, DOI: 10.1111/csp2.248.

734 UNep, 2019: Effectiveness of policy interventions relating to the illegal and unsustainable
735 wildlife trade pp. 1–28. United Nations Environment Programme, Nairobi, Kenya.

736 Wang, L.F., and B.T. Eaton, 2007: Bats, civets and the emergence of SARS. *Curr. Top.*
737 *Microbiol. Immunol.* **315**, 325–44, DOI: 10.1007/978-3-540-70962-6_13.

738 Wegner, G.I., K.A. Murray, M. Springmann, A. Muller, S.H. Sokolow, K. Saylor, and D.M.
739 Morens, 2022: Averting wildlife-borne infectious disease epidemics requires a focus
740 on socio-ecological drivers and a redesign of the global food system. *Eclinicalmedicine*
741 **47**, 101386, DOI: 10.1016/j.eclinm.2022.101386.

742 Woezik, A.F.G. van, L.M.A. Braakman-Jansen, O. Kulyk, L. Siemons, and J.E.W.C. van
743 Gemert-Pijnen, 2016: Tackling wicked problems in infection prevention and control: a
744 guideline for co-creation with stakeholders. *Antimicrob. Resist. Infect. Control* **5**, 20,
745 DOI: 10.1186/s13756-016-0119-2.

746 Woldehanna, S., and S. Zimicki, 2015: An expanded One Health model: Integrating social
747 science and One Health to inform study of the human-animal interface. *Soc. Sci. Med.*
748 **129**, 87–95, DOI: 10.1016/j.socscimed.2014.10.059.